

Exploring the Diagnosis of the Nigerian Economic Depression

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Abstract

Economic depression seems to be synonymous with Nigerian economy in recent years as there has been serious contracting of the country's gross domestic product since the 1st quarter of 2016. This article explores how Nigeria got into economic depression and found that counterproductive and unclear policies of government particularly in economic matters, exacerbated by dwindling revenue created panic and discouraged investors which worsened the situation. The paper, at the end, calls for urgent policy that can grease and encourage economic diversification of the country through increased transparency, strengthening various governmental and non-governmental institutions, provisions of lasting infrastructure, and citizens' participation in the process of governance. The study equally recommends the need to restore the confidence of investors through clear-cut economic policies and for the essential infrastructural expenditure of government to be increased.

Keywords: Economic depression, Economic growth, Gross domestic product, Underemployment, Unemployment

Introduction

Economic depression is a long-term economic downturn that occasions slow economic activities in economies of a country. It is usually characterized by unemployment increase, lesser business revenues, lack of social good and social balance, instability in the forest market or volatility of a nation's currency, reduced amount of commerce and trade, stock market crash, prices deflation, bank failures and other economic difficulties that result to financial crisis of a country (Ojokoh, Olaku, Sarumi & Olotu, 2021).

Nigerian has been in deep economic depression since 2016. In the words World Bank (2020), the gross domestic product (GDP) of Nigeria grew only by 0.36%, which shows a decline in the 1st quarter of 2016. This was further declined with a 2.06%. The GDP appreciated by 2.24% and 1.30% respectively in the 3rd and 4th quarter of 2016, indicating a continuous decline. Nigeria was still in economic depression as at 1st quarter of 2017, and Nigeria's GDP growth was equally negative at 0.52%. African Research Bulletin (2017) contended that challenges such as rising unemployment, weakened currency, and hyper-inflation worsened Nigeria's dire economic situation. The continuous contraction of the Nigeria's GDP pushed many Nigerians to under-employment and out of employment which affected the citizens' purchasing power and further caused stagnant wages and weak currency. Awojulgbe (2017) observed that unemployment rose to 12.1 percent from 10.4 percent during the 1st quarter of 2016, while underemployment rose to 19.1 percent from 18.7 percent during the same quarter. Unemployment and underemployment rose continuously for the 2nd quarter of 2016. As underemployment rose to 13.3 percent, unemployment rose to 19.3 percent.

The Vanguard (2017) noted that underemployment and unemployment rose to 19.7% and 13.9% respectively in the 3rd quarter of 2016. It is equally observed by Olawoyin (2017) that the rise in underemployment and unemployment continued in the 4th quarter of 2016 as underemployment and unemployment stood at 21.0% and 14.2% respectively. The Nigeria's inflation rate was double digit during the same period and sometimes rose to over 18.0% (Nwoba, Nwonu & Agbaeze, 2017). While many employees in the private sector are being retrenched, public sector employees are being owed salaries and paid a fraction of their salaries.

This necessitated the present study that explores how Nigeria can come out of its economic depression.

The Immediate Causes and Effects of Nigerian Economic Depression

Nigerian economy is dependent on oil despite non-oil sectors making some contributions. Adejumo, Ajide, Adeniran & Alimi (2021) observed that 91.74 percent of the Nigeria's GDP was accounted by oil sector during the 2nd quarter of 2016. The crude oil oversupply in the global market, alternative energy sources and increased energy efficiency resulted to a sharp drop in the global oil price. This caused the foreign exchange of Nigeria to drastically reduced. The increased number of hostilities during the regime of the immediate past president, Muhammadu Buhari, by some militants under the umbrella of Niger Delta Avengers resulted to many oil pipelines to be blown up, which reduced the Nigeria's daily oil supply to the international market.

From mid – 2014, the price of oil in the global market has been on a downward slide. Vanguard (2016) observed a continuous slide in the oil sector to as low as \$28 per barrel from December 2015 to January 2016 from the previous trading at \$100 per barrel in 2014. The transition of China, the biggest manufacturer in the world, to service-based economy from their previous industrial-based economy, global oil oversupply, and decline in the global energy needs occasioned the decline in the global oil price. Magner (2016) averred that the transition of China's economy resulted to their less oil demand. The advanced technology in American oil mining and breakthrough in the United States shale oil production resulted to their very little demand for oil and self-sufficiency in crude oil.

Puko (2015) noted that the United States that used to be the biggest buyer of Nigeria's crude oil stopped purchasing crude oil from Nigeria after lifting a 40year restriction that earlier imposed on American companies from exporting American oil. More so, the signing of historic agreement between Iran and the United States occasioned the end of the some of the United States imposed sanctions on Iran, which increased Iranian global oil supply to almost 4million oil barrels per day (OPEC, 2016). These caused global crude oil oversupply and resulted to low

oil price. It equally resulted to a weak Naira currency, low Nigeria foreign exchange earnings, and made the Nigerian government to experience difficulties in meeting its budgetary demands and accrue enormous deficits.

Niger Delta Avengers (NDA), a new militant group in the Niger Delta region began destruction and vandalization of oil pipelines and other oil installations in 2015. The group attacked virtually half of crude oil production in Nigeria and brought about reduction in oil supply to Nigerian power stations, which resulted to sharp drop in electricity supply to industries and households in Nigeria. For instance, the Forcados Shell Terminal destruction by NDA on March 25, 2016 caused Nigeria not to export 380,000 barrels of oil per day, which resulted to a huge loss of \$2 billion for the country as at the end of September 2016 (Ozougwu, Madu, Chukwuorji, Ozougwu & Ozougwu, 2023).

The abrupt implementation, by Muhammad Buhari-the immediate past president, of Treasury Single Account (TSA) when money was insufficiently flowing in the country occasioned reduction in deposits and made it extremely difficult for individuals and businesses to transact their businesses and obtain loans. More so, the adopted non-liberal policy on foreign-exchange during the Buhari's regime was counterproductive. As dollar was pegged at N199 by the government, the black market value of the same dollar rose to 500. The decision of the government to exclude certain items from accessing government's provided foreign exchange at official rate and allow few individuals who were willing to import essential goods and machineries to produce in the country created huge abuse and corruption in the policy as some persons who were close to those at the corridor of power accessed dollars at the government official rate (Sanusi, 2016). The policy impeded the growth of Nigerian local industries as people who were close to those in corridors of power found it more lucrative and attractive to sell dollars they acquired at the N199 official rate per US dollar for N500 per US dollar in the black market.

The inconsistency of the government's policies created distress and caused loss in the foreign direct investment (FDI) while dousing optimism for local investment. This resulted to JP Morgan Chase & Co of America to delist Nigeria from its Government Bond Index for Emerging Markets (Ogunwale & Shosanya, 2015). The uncertainty in the government's foreign exchange

policy caused many industries to relocate abroad and huge loss of jobs because of its obscureness. Babatunde (2016) observed that Africa's largest manufacturer of tomato paste, Erisco Foods, announced its intention to relocate to china as a result of the frustrations they were encountering in obtaining foreign exchange which compounded unemployment and underemployment issues in Nigeria. Onuoha and Okon (2016) observed that 272 firms were forced out of business, and 50 of the 272 firms were manufacturing companies because of the inconsistencies in the exchange market. Additionally, apart from some of the affected companies relocating to Nigeria's neighbouring countries, 222 small-scale businesses in the country closed shops, occasioning 180,000 job losses.

As the state government are finding it difficult to pay salaries, private sectors are massively retrenching workers. The heavy reliance on federal allocation by the state governments compounded the issues. The huge dependence on oil earning by the federal government created smaller federal government allocations to the state governments due to drop in production and price of oil. Bailout funds were issued by the federal government to the state governments to ensure they pay workers' salaries. Nonetheless, the bailouts only made little achievements as most of the states did not waste time to exhaust the bailouts and found it difficult to service them due to paltriness in their monthly allocations from the federal government. Only Enugu, Rivers, and Lagos states, as at mid-2016, were viable financially and succeeded in funding their recurrent expenditure from their monthly earnings (Chinedu & Ogochukwu, 2016). Many states were not able to meet their monthly recurrent expenditure despite the release of Paris Refund to state governments.

How Nigeria can get out of Economic Depression

For Nigeria to get out of its economic depression, long-term and short-term measures are urgently needed to be taken. In the short-term, the government urgently needs to restore the confidence of the investors through adopting sensible and clear-cut economic policies. First, both the former president, Muhammad Buhari, and the present president, Bola Ahmed Tinubu, committed economic blunders by waiting for several months after winning elections before their

cabinets were named, which created huge uncertainties and panic that pushed many foreign investors to exit the country. It appears both regimes lack clear-cut economic policies in place. For instance, the headed economic management team by Yemi Osibanjo, the immediate past vice president, was devoid of technocrats and economists that could offer sound economic-policy suggestions that can boost Nigeria's fortune. Wakil (2016) observed that the vice president, finance minister, central bank governor, directors and ministers of the former regime constituted the economic management team.

In attempts to fight corruption and plug the financial leakages, the administrations micromanaged every dimension of Nigeria's existence without heeding to expert suggestions, which created panic and occasioned antithetical results. The services of career technocrats and economists should be engaged by the government to proffer economic policies that are pragmatic and essential in addressing the arduous economic challenges confronting Nigeria. Putting in place right economic team will water the ground for non-itinerant economic policies to be take and restore investors' confidence. The monetary and fiscal policies of Nigeria need to be adjusted urgently in order to reflect the current economic mood.

As Chigbu and Michael (2013) observed, fiscal policy in economics concerns itself with using government revenue collection and expenses to influence a country's economy. It pays special attention to the overall impact of outcome of budget on economic activities. It is pertinent to note that fiscal policy can equally be contrasted with the monetary policy that focuses on stabilizing the economy, and controlling supply of money and interest rates. Taxation and government spending are the two key instruments of fiscal policy. Yakubu and Abdul-Jalil (2016) observed that any change in the composition and level of taxation and government spending impacts on the distribution of income, pattern of resource allocation, and aggregate demand and the level of economic activity.

In the light of the current economic depression, the study proposes expansionary fiscal policy that would increase the income of Nigerians after tax and improve the amount of money in the hands of Nigerian citizens which they can now spend. Granted obvious difficulties are associated with the above proposition, to wits:

A. Won't the money end up in black hole due to inefficiencies and corruption?

B. What are the things government should spend on?

C. Where would the money come from?

Since drop in oil and activities of economic saboteurs have caused huge reduction in our revenue, the only necessary option to the government is for them to borrow. The government is much aware of it and has been borrowing (Igbodika, Jessie & Andabai, 2016; Umoru, 2016). Public opinions and economic commentators are always against governments' borrowing due to the challenges posed by debt servicing. However, if not embezzled and applied to the right sector, borrowing is beneficial. Borrowing to fund capital projects, and not recurrent expenditure, is advisable. More so, since oil is indisputably essential to the economic engine of Nigerian government, the government should try to find a way of dialoguing with the Niger Delta militants to cease hostilities and stop pipeline vandalism.

There has been recurrent decimal of militancy in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria ever since oil was discovered in the region as some youths from the region resorted to arms because of their feeling of marginalization despite crude oil, that is the mainstay of Nigeria's foreign exchange, being domiciled in their land. The destructive impact of crude oil exploration equally created misgivings among youths from the region. The federal and state governments are urged to integrate measures that can address the reservations of the region and not paper over them, and global best practices should be adopted in crude oil exploration in the region. Most importantly, Nigeria urgently needs to move away her economy from oil dependency through diversification of its economy in order to wade off future economic uncertainties created by fluctuation in oil price in the global market. To achieve this purpose, the government urgently needs to solidify and provide qualitative security in the country, create durable infrastructure, and implement policies that would spur foreign and local investments in the country.

The Nigerian environment is too fragile for investment despite having a large labour force and a huge market. This is caused by insecurity, poor power supply, unfavorable policies, and non-existent infrastructure, which have driven many foreign investments away. Most of the companies that were carrying out their businesses in the country have shut down their operations and relocated to neighboring countries and new ventures sadly lack incentives to put their investments in the country. Prilleri, Michellin, Dunlop and etc are part of notable ventures that have shutdown their operations and relocated elsewhere. Ekanem (2024) observed that Tower Aluminium, Etisalat, WEMPCO, Evans Medicals, GlaxoSmithKline Nigeria, Procter and Gamble (P&G) and ShopRite have shutdown their operations in Nigeria. It is necessary for the government to do their best in making business processes easy in Nigeria. World Bank (2020) observed that Nigerian is placed 169 out of the 190 ranked countries on the institution's ranking on easy of doing business. Therefore, durable infrastructure is urgently needed to make easy for businesses to operate.

It is sad that most households and firms still generate their own power as a result of government's provided erratic power supply in the country, despite the problem of power supply being one of the major issues since independence. With more than 220 million people in Nigeria, the country cannot generate up to 5,000 MW, which is very discouraging. This is worsened by attacks on oil installations in the country, which has compounded the country's power issues. Nigeria's power issues should be addressed before her economy can be made viable. Despite being the most populous nation and largest economy in Africa, Nigeria is still having lowest per capital consumption of electricity in Africa. Akinwale and Ogundari (2017) observed that Nigeria consumes only 142kWh per capita of electricity while South Africa consumes 4,326kWh per capita of the same electricity. There must be ways to provide constant and cheap electric power supply by a country that is seeking to attract foreign and local investments. For years, power supply has not improved in Nigeria despite it being a key promise during every electioneering campaign (Owete, 2016). Nigeria must provide power by leveraging on her comparative advantages since power supply is fundamental prerequisite in the development of the country. More so, national interest should not be sacrificed in the current push for green

energy. Clearly, plans for green energy should be drawn by Nigeria, but we should exploit traditional power sources while waiting for plans on clear energy to mature.

The transport system of Nigeria is laden with intractable challenges that have made markets-accessibility very difficult. Roads are the major channel of transportation in Nigeria, and most Nigerian roads have sadly become accident scenes and are in bad shapes. Apart from inadequacy of the roads, most of the Nigerian roads are old and cannot contain burgeoning traffic caused by high population increase. This has created accidents, congestions, high transport fares, and increased transport time for the citizens and foreigners. The challenge is compounded by worn out bridges that are in serious need of replacement, but nothing has been done. It is indisputable that availability of good transport systems is necessary for a country's economic activities because it creates room for more favorable business. As such, Nigeria has to urgently improve her road network.

Transportation is very necessary for economic activities, and the availability of good transport networks would make business more favorable. As a result, Nigeria must urgently expand their transport routes, carryout regular repair to control burgeoning traffic, build new roads across the country in order to improve generally her road networks. The modernization of the railway network must be done, and more railway routes have to be created to easy conveyance of people and products across the country. Spending on infrastructure (for instance, transportation and power) would yield positive and transformative outcomes, and returns on borrowed money would accrue within a short period of time, while the Nigeria's crude oil dependency would wither away gradually.

Since the oil sector is still essential despite the urgent call for diversification of the economy, Nigerian government must act on plugging revenue losses in the oil sector that are caused by inefficient exploration processes, oil bunkering, and pipeline vandalism. First, the government must address the negative impact of oil exploration on the Niger Delta environments. This is because militancy was birthed by neglect of Niger Delta people, and concerns of the Niger Delta region must be addressed before oil exploration in the region can be operated in peaceful environment. Nigeria's government must engage in activities such as petrochemicals and crude oil refinery and not just engaging in crude oil sale as its only economic activity. For sake of transparency and efficiency , the oil sector needs to be urgently

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deregulated to yield more returns to the country and create more job opportunities for teeming population of Nigeria.

The government needs to re-energize the agricultural sector in order to improve the GDP contribution of the country through establishment of agro-allied ventures and make the country self-sufficient in food production. Government must provide necessary incentives that would attract investors such as qualitative power supply, low tax, and cheap lands. This does not vitiate the fact that Nigeria needs investment from the private sector to sufficiently and transformative develop her agricultural sector. With proper incentives to attract investors, good transport networks, and constant power supply, agro-allied and non-agro-allied manufacturing would take deeper root in the country and manufactured goods can easily compete with goods manufactured in other countries. The Ajaokuta Steel Plant, government owned refineries and other similar industries should be privatized and revamped. In fact, industrial revolution is urgently needed in the country.

Most importantly, it is only the political willingness of the Nigerian government that can drive the aforementioned suggested policies. The government must allow independent bodies to be practically independent and strengthen her institutions in order to wade off corruption that has been bane in Nigeria's development and recurring decimal. It is pertinent to note that in a corrupt system, siphoning of money for private purpose and conflict of interest will be the order of the day, and no economic policies can be successfully implemented if corruption is not efficiently and effectively fought.

There is need for clear foreign policy to be adopted by Nigeria in respect of its economic engagement with other countries. The policy must ensure that jobs meant for Nigerians are not exported to other countries by multinational companies, and that foreign expatriates abide by the country's laid down regulations and rules on the cause of their operation in Nigeria. Nigerian government should explore ways of signing deals with foreign companies of products Nigerians consume in large quantities to establish branches of their companies in the country. Ethiopia adopted such measure and it effectively worked for them (Sanusi, 2016).

There should be sense of patriotism among Nigerians before the country can come out of economic depression. Nigerian citizens must be pushful in seeing the success of the country by treating and seeing the country as a personal property and not just engage in their individual

pursuits. Nigerian citizens were aloof in engaging their public office holders, until recently. It is important to state a country whose citizens fail to engage their political leadership would always not receive the desired leadership. Nigerians need to be constructively questioning actions and policies of government, and engaging political office holders constantly in order to improve the country and its leadership quality. Finally, the citizens should be scrutinizing budget expenditure by public office holders in order to ascertain the sincerity of the public officers and their progress, which would assist the citizens in making informed decisions during elections and assist in electing credible leaders with cogent and compelling plans on how to address the problems confronting the country.

Conclusion

It is paradoxical that Nigeria is suffering in the midst of plenty occasioned since finding of petroleum in the country. The country will remain in economic depression if government sustains its current posture. Howbeit, adopting the above enumerated measures would assist the country in getting out of economic depression. The road projects, rail, and power would boost Nigeria's economic activities and enhance its easy of doing business. Effective power supply and huge population would make companies site their production plants in Nigeria. The government needs to restore the confidence of investors by changing its policy directions through implementing sound and clear economic policies and upgrading its infrastructural facilities in order to get out of Nigeria's economic depression. Nigerian must diversify and stabilize her economy by incorporating other sectors and breaking away from dependency on oil.

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